

The Application of ERP on the Users' Emotional Reactions to the Web Page Design

Yu-Min Fang *, Ming-Huang Lin **

*National Taiwan University of Science and Technology, Department of Industrial and Commercial Design, First International Computer Corporation, Depart of Design
43 Keelung Road, Section 4, Taipei, Taiwan, Phone: 886-2-55998856
E-mail: geoffrey_fang@pcg.fic.com.tw

** National Chiao Tung University, Institute of Applied Arts, Ta Hsueh Road, Hsinchu, Taiwan 300, ROC, Phone: 886-3-5712121 Ext. 58309
E-mail: ludwiglin@mail.nctu.edu.tw

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Abstract: Globally accessible web sites enable corporations to communicate with a wide variety of constituencies and represent a resource for any organization seeking a broad audience. Designing a web page with the appropriate responses from users is the crucial key of the successful communication. Although many design guidelines and principles are provided by user interface specialists, but few scientific analyses and confirmations are carried out to verify these common rules or hypotheses. Do users respond the designed web page as effectively and positively as what the design specialists' claim? What kind of web page design will arise the positive emotions? This research employs the method of ERP (Event-related potential) studies to detect brainwave variations by asking subjects to watch the different formats of web pages, to see if there is any specific emotional and physical activity associated with different formats of web pages.

The stimuli include seven groups of web pages, illustrating different formats of presenting products, and each group presents four different electrical home appliances products, including men's face shaver, women's shaver, toasters, and irons. The seven formats of presenting products are the combination results of the different visual stimuli - brief descriptions (texts), product photos, human faces, and bodies. In order to control the extraneous variable, a typical background of the commercial web page was chosen and revised. All stimuli share the same background. Three components are then carefully examined: 1) P300, evoked by visual attention, 2) N170, usually associated with face recognition. 3) N400, evoked by semantic confusion.

The results evidence that web pages with different presentation format do evoke subjects' varied ERPs latency and amplitude. And parts of the results confirm the interface experts' suggestion. The detailed findings, first of all, shows that on the PZ and CZ location of the scalp, stimuli Group 1 (brief description of the product)

generates more amplitude of P300 but delay the latency. It suggests that simply providing the brief description of products consumes subjects more time to react to the messages, and maybe generates more effort on cognition processing if viewers spend the same time on viewing the screen. Secondly, N170 analysis displays that the appearance of face on web page did evoke greater N170 on the T5 location of the scalp. Thirdly, subjects' response behavior (the mouse-clicking data) exhibits that the web page with text along is less attractive, and the web pages presenting the photos of products are more attractive.

Key words: web page design, ERP, emotion,

1. Introduction

Globally accessible web sites enable corporations to communicate with a wide variety of constituencies and represent a resource for any organization seeking a broad audience (Iwaarden, Wiele, and Ball. 2004). Designing a web page with the appropriate responses from viewers is the crucial key of the successful communication. Although many design guidelines and principles are provided by user interface specialists, but few scientific analyses and confirmations are carried out to verify these common rules or hypotheses (Fang, 2003). Do users respond the designed web page as effectively and positively as what the design specialists' claim? What kind of web page design will arise the emotions?

1.1 The Current Measurement Method in Design research

In many design studies, the popular method of measuring subjects' emotion toward the design objects is applying adjective descriptions of the semantic differences (SD) and further to the multidimensional scale (MDS), for example, the numerous research into Kansei Engineering in Japan (Nagamachi, 1995), and the research in multidimensional space (Green, Carmone, and Smith, 1989. Hsiao and Chen, 1997). They use questionnaires with Liker Scale, mostly based on the Semantics Analysis developed by Osgood in 1957, to acquire the subject's subjective responses to the stimuli. But skeptical criticism to this measurement arises frequently since that 1) the subjects' respond might be misguided by questionnaire design, 2) the insufficient reliability and accuracy, and 3) the distrust about subjects' patient with answering all questions.

Nevertheless, through the development in science and technology in recent years, the objective psychological response can be measured by the physiological signal, utilizing the scientific instrument without causing any negative influence on the mankind, such as EEG (electroencephalogram), ERP, EMG (electromyogram) , EOG (electrooculogram) , ECG(electrocardiogram) , BP (blood pressure), etc.. To supplement the insufficiency of the current measurement method in design research, objective scientific instrument might be useful and can be borrowed to examine the subjects' mental emotion stimulated by viewing the web

pages.

1.2 The ERPs Research on the Emotional Processing of Visual Stimuli

This research employs the method of ERP (Event-related potential) studies, as a new tool for interface design assessment, to detect brainwave variations by asking subjects to watch the different formats of web pages. ERPs are voltage fluctuations that are associated in time with some physical or mental occurrence, and can provide important information about how the human brain normally processes information. These potentials can be recorded from the human scalp and extracted from the ongoing electroencephalogram (EEG) by means of filtering and signal averaging (Picton et al., 2000) (Fig. 1, 2).

Figure 1~2 An electrode position map on the scalp, the real-time waveform recorded from the electroencephalogram

The first study utilizing the ERPs on the emotional processing of visual stimuli was by Johnston and co-workers. They established that some late components of ERPs could reflect the emotional processing of different visual stimuli (Johnston, Burleson, & Miller, 1987; Johnston, Miller, & Burleson, 1986). Several research groups have also reported that the positive ERP component P300 is evoked specifically by emotional pictures (Naumann et al., 1992; Diedrich et al., 1997; Palomba et al., 1997). The P300 is the classic index of attention, recognition, and stimulus probability (Donchin and Coles, 1988). And the emotionally positive and negative stimuli evoked greater P300 amplitudes than neutral ones (Palomba, Angrilli, &

Bravi, 1993).

In the other cognitive literature, N170 and N400 are associated with this research as well. The N170 is the index of facial recognition, and the visual encoding of this cognition processing has been reported at around 170 ms (Allison et al. 1994; Puce et al. 1997). The N400 is associated with the emotion of confusion. ERP studies have elicited a large negative component peaking around 400 ms (N400 effect) by presenting incongruent (relative to congruent) word pairs, or unrelated pictures (Kutas and Hillyard, 1980; Barrett, Rugg, and Perrett, 1988).

In this study, the researchers try to manipulate the different visual stimuli of web page, the different groups of combinations of brief descriptions (texts), product photos, human faces, and human bodies, to see if these ERPs components mentioned above can be evoked. Three components are carefully examined: 1) P300, evoked by visual attention, 2) N170, usually associated with face recognition. 3) Furthermore, by presenting incongruent visual stimuli on one web page (e.g. presenting male's face with female's shaver, or presenting female's nude body with male's shaver), N400 is assumed to be evoked.

2. Research Devices and Analysis Software

Hardware of ERPs instrument includes two systems: "Physiological Data Record System" and "Visual Image Display System", developed by Compumedics Neuroscan, USA. Physiological Data Record System consists of three systems: an **electrode** positioning system (elastic fabric head cap with 40 sintered Ag/AgCl electrodes, Quick-Cap, Fig. 3), a 40 channel monopolar digital amplifier, which connects to the computer via USB, (NuAmps, Fig. 4), and an acquisition and analysis software, for processing and analyzing ERP data, (SCAN 4.3, Fig. 5). To construct this system, the Quick-Cap should be connected to the NuAmps, and to the computer with installed acquisition and analysis software SCAN4.3.

Figure 3~6 Quick-Cap 40ch, NuAmps 40 channels, SCAN 4.3, the ongoing experiment

Visual Image Display System, displayed by a 17" computer monitor, is a browser interface which presents digital images for custom stimulus and task design (STIM²). Through STIM², the stimuli are put in, and the display time, interval, and sequence are determined. Then these two systems are connected. The subjects are requested to watch the web page images and answer questions by clicking the mouse. The researcher can observe the ongoing experiment through another monitor (Fig. 6). The STIM² controls time setting and provides the time signal to the SCAN 4.3 while recording the data. The mixed data can be analyzed later by the analysis software.

3. Method

3.1 Subject

10 of the graduate and undergraduate students of National Taiwan University of Science and Technology were selected for the experiments. There are 6 male and 4 female, whose mean age is 23 years old, 4 of them are with design background. None of the subjects has neural disease of visual illness or brain injury.

3.2 Stimuli

The stimuli of this experiment include 7 groups of web pages (Table 1), illustrating seven formats of presenting products, and each group presents four different electrical home appliances products, including men's face shaver, women's shaver, toasters, and irons (Table 2). The seven formats of presenting products are the combination results of the different visual stimuli - brief descriptions (texts), product photos, human faces, and bodies. The seven groups of web pages are: Group 1 (brief description of the product), Group 2 (brief description of the product plus the product photo), Group 3 (the product photo along), Group 4 (the photo of product and human face with strong relation), Group 5 (the photo of product and human body with strong relation), Group 6 (the photo of product and human face with less relation),

and Group 7 (the photo of product and human body with less relation).

In order to control the extraneous variable, a typical background of the commercial web page (The home page of Philips, Taiwan) was chosen and revised. All stimuli share the same background.

Table 1 Seven groups of web pages illustrate seven formats of presenting products

Group	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
Descrip- tion	Brief description of the product	brief description of the product plus the product photo	the product photo along	the photo of product and human face with strong relation
Web Pages Example				
Group	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	/
Descrip- tion	the photo of product and human body with strong relation	the photo of product and human face with less relation	the photo of product and human body with less relation	
Web Pages Example				

Table 2 The four different types of electrical appliances products as stimuli

products	men's face shaver	women's shaver	toasters	irons
Web Pages Example				

3.3 Procedure

After short briefing, the subject seated on a comfortable chair and wore electrode cap. Then the subject was instructed to watch the web page images and answer questions (“Is this web page attractive?”) by clicking the mouse. If the subject agreed with this question, they clicked left-button, if not, the right-button. The stimuli appeared one by one for 1.5 seconds, and inter-trial interval was 0.5 seconds. To avoid Oddball Effect, each stimulus in Group 1, 2, 3 randomly presents 20 times, but web pages in Group 4, 5, 6, 7 presents 10 times, since subjects might regard the photos of products with male or female human faces as the same group, and the photos of products with male or female human bodies as well. There are totally 400 trials each person. An experiment lasts about 13 minutes.

3.4 Recording

EEG was recorded by 40 electrodes Ag/AgCl sintered electrode cap (Quick cap, Compumedics Neuroscan, USA). Electrode positions included the standard 10-20 system locations and additional intermediate positions. Horizontal and vertical EOG were monitored using four facial electrodes laces on the outer canthi of the eyes and in the inferior and superior areas of the orbit. EEG was continuously recorded, digitized at a rate of 1000 Hz with a linked mastoids reference. The signal was amplified by Nuamps (Compumedics Neuroscan, USA), band-pass filtered at 0.1-40 Hz. We performed epoching 100 ms prior to and 800 ms after stimulus onset. After VEOG correction and rejection of artifacts ($-75/75 \mu\text{V}$ threshold), the average proceed directly related to the stimuli.

3.5. Data reduction and analysis

The subjects’ data, recorded by ERPs data record system, is then preceded by statistic operation and examined by the analysis software (SCAN 4.3). Figure 7 shows the averages obtained once the baseline was subtracted from each ERP. According to the suggestion of ERPs studies, three possible earlier components, P300, N170 and N400, are frequently evoked by visual stimuli during special context of emotional stimulation. Thus in the study P300 (identified with the interval between 270 and 450 msec), N170 (identified with the interval between 130 and 180 msec), and N400 (identified with the interval between 380 and 500 msec)

especially distributed along the midline of brain are investigated. Mean amplitudes were calculated from this intervals. ANOVA were performed with electrode location (Fz, Cz, Pz, Cpz, T5, T6) and stimuli group (group1-7) as within-subject factors. Post-hoc comparison were made to determine the significance of pairwise contrasts, using Tukey's two-factor HSD procedure ($p < 0.05$).

4. Result

The subjects' waveform, recorded from different location of scalp, were integrated and summarized as following:

(1) One of the purposes of this study is to see if there is any effect of presenting product photo on web page, comparing with the only brief description (text along). Because P300 is associated with the attention and emotional visual stimulus, so its amplitudes and latency is carefully examined. The analysis result shows that on the PZ and CZ location of the scalp, the latency of physical occurrence of P300 results in significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between Group 1, 2, and 3 (Table 3). And the sequence of the latency of recognition processes is: Group 1 (Brief description of the product) > Group 2 (Product Name + the product photo) > Group 3 (the product photo along).

Item		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Sig.
P300_Latency (PZ)	Group 1	409.60	40.492	12.805	.001
	Group 2	361.30	52.641	16.647	
	Group 3	327.90	38.791	12.267	
P300_Peak_amplitude (PZ)	Group 1	7.7607	5.98831	1.89367	.590
	Group 2	5.1304	5.17531	1.63658	
	Group 3	5.9028	6.26414	1.98089	
P300_Latency (CZ)	Group 1	405.10	42.720	13.509	.015
	Group 2	375.10	59.015	18.662	
	Group 3	336.10	44.596	14.102	
P300_Peak_amplitude (CZ)	Group 1	3.4527	6.24097	1.97357	.350
	Group 2	-.0412	5.48500	1.73451	
	Group 3	.1082	6.17972	1.95420	

Figure 7 The voltage fluctuation waveform of PZ

Table 3 The latency and the peak amplitude of Group 1, 2, and 3 on PZ, P300.

If we compare the peak amplitude of P300, there are no significant difference ($P>0.05$) between Group 1, 2, and 3. But statistical analysis and waveform graphic suggests that Group 1 generates more amplitude of P300 (Fig. 7 and Table 3). It means that the brief description (text along) on the web page may consume subjects more time period in reacting to the messages, but evokes stronger attention and cognition processing. Furthermore, there are no significant difference ($P>0.05$) between Group 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 if we compare the P300. It means that presenting different photos (products, human faces, or human bodies) on web page does not evoke different waveform of the P300.

(2) The negative ERP component N170 is usually associated with the face recognition processes. In this study, it tried to understand if the presentation of human face on the web page evoked ERP component N170. The result shows that on the T5 location of the scalp, the peak amplitude of N170 is significantly different ($P<0.05$) between Group 3, 4, and 5 (Fig. 8 and Table 4). And the sequence of the peak amplitude is: Group 4 (product photo with face) > Group 5 (product photo with human body) > Group 3 (the product photo along). It means that the appearance of face (Group 4, 5) on web page did evoke N170 on the T5 location of the scalp.

Fig. 8 Voltage fluctuation waveform of T5

Item		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Sig.
N170_Latency (T5)	Group 3	150.80	9.987	3.158	.392
	Group 4	147.30	9.499	3.004	
	Group 5	153.00	8.083	2.556	
N170_Peak_amplitude (T5)	Group 3	.9647	1.33570	.42239	.000
	Group 4	-2.3006	1.28863	.40750	
	Group 5	-.0841	1.91571	.60580	

Table 4 the latency and t the peak amplitude of N170 of Group 3, 4, and 5 on T5, N170.

(3) The subjects were instructed to watch the stimuli and answer questions about the attractiveness of the web pages by clicking the mouse. On the user's click, the subjects' response data were recorded by ERPs data record system, and were integrated and summarized (set value of attractive=1, unattractive=2). The result shows that the attractiveness of the web pages is significantly different ($P < 0.05$) between these 7 groups of presentation style (Table 5). The subjects' preference of the web pages is that, 1) Group 1 (text along) is less attractive; 2) The web pages presenting the photos of products are more attractive; 3) However, these response behavior (this mouse-clicking data) is not strong enough to prove that the human faces or bodies make the web pages more attractive, because the previous ERPs examination is not significantly different among Group 3~7.

Group	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	1.81	0.39
2	1.27	0.44
3	1.24	0.43
4	1.29	0.45
5	1.26	0.44
6	1.31	0.45
7	1.32	0.46

Table 5 Attractiveness of the 7 groups of web pages

(4) The negative ERP component N400 is usually associated with the subjects' emotion of confusion in incongruent situation. By stimuli manipulation (e.g. presenting male's face with female's shaver, or presenting female's nude body with male's shaver), this research was trying to evoke N400. But comparing Group 4 and 5 (reasonable combinations of product photos and human faces or bodies) with group 6 and 7 (unreasonable situation), the result shows that there was no evidence of evoking N400. It might suggest that the situation of unrelated photos on the web page is not strong enough to evoke subjects' emotional confusion when viewers search the web site.

5. Conclusions

1. By analyzing the subjects' positive ERP component P300 evoked by the different web page, the result shows that on the PZ and CZ location of the scalp, stimuli Group 1 (brief description of the product) generates more amplitude of P300 but delay the latency. It

means that simply providing the brief description of products consumes subjects more time to react to the messages, and maybe generates more effort on cognition processing if viewers spend the same time on viewing the screen. For this reason, avoiding large amount of text on the web page will help to communicate the target audiences before they lose their patient. This conclusion supports some of the interface design guidelines.

2. By analyzing N170, it shows that the appearance of face (and human body) on web page did evoke N170 on the T5 location of the scalp. Therefore, adding the human figure on the web pages might be useful for attracting viewers to activate the face recognition processing, but there is no evidence in this study that it improves the attractiveness of the web pages.
3. By studying subjects' response behavior (this mouse-clicking data) about the attractiveness of the web pages, the result shows that the web page with text along is less attractive, and the web pages presenting the photos of products are more attractive. This result matches the design principle proposed by interface experts.

The results evidence that web pages with different presenting format do evoke subjects' varied ERPs latency and amplitude. Parts of the results justify the interface experts' suggestion. And the data acquired from the electroencephalogram of brain activity are valuable for the further analysis. However, the knowledge of Neuroscience and application of ERPs in web design is rather new in design research, which needs to be carefully studied in order to gather correct and useful information.

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